

SUPPLEMENTARY MATERIALS AND METHODS

Isoform switch analysis. For isoform switch analysis, we performed splice-aware alignment using the Kallisto aligner (version 0.50.1)¹. Transcript abundance was calculated based on mouse gene and transcript annotations (Genecode Mouse Version M33). Isoform switch identification and quantification were performed using transcript level abundance values with the IsoformSwitchAnalyzeR R package (version 2.1.3)². Isoform switches were compared between groups using differential gene expression analysis. Identified switches were subjected to functional analysis, including the prediction of coding potential with CPC2³, domain detection with PFAM⁴, prediction of Intrinsically Disordered Regions with IUPred2A⁵, and cellular localization with analyzeDeepLoc2⁶.

RESULTS

Gene isoform switch analysis. In classical RNAseq data processing pipelines, gene expression is considered gene length-normalized read counts mapped on the genomic region assigned to that gene according to the annotation. The functional meaning of gene expression is the raw approximation of protein quantity in cells. However, in some instances, expressions calculated this way will not present a quantity of gene-encoded proteins. This can be caused by alternative splicing and/or altered function of the splicing machinery due to some external factors. In these cases, the processed mRNA of the gene can have a distinct function or be non-functional. Splicing can be affected by DNA mutations that occur on the splice site regions or DNA regions that encode proteins of the spliceosome machinery. A few examples of alternative splicing are presented in **Supplementary Figure 1A**, which can affect the function of encoded proteins by skipping exons or retaining introns. Alternative splicing has been shown to have a significant effect in many cancers⁷. Another factor that may affect splicing is that ionizing radiation can induce DNA mutations. Macaeva et al.⁸ showed that cells irradiated with different doses of X-rays (0.1 and 1.0 Gy) showed elevated gene splicing. In cases where alternative splicing causes opposite changes in isoform expression, when one isoform is expressed more and the other less, changes on the level of gene expression cannot be detected.

To detect the potential functional effect of switched isoforms, we performed isoform switch analysis to evaluate the expression of multi-transcript genes. RNA sequencing showed that most genes (> 84%) had only one transcript expressed. Moreover, only a few genes showed significant changes. Four isoform switches (*Cdc34*, *Cetn2*, *Rps7*, and *Stoml2*) were detected in the LVs of male mice 440 days post-simGCRsim-IR (**Supplementary Figure 1B**). In female mice, four (*Eif2s2*, *Rpl18a*, *Xdh*, and *Stoml2*) and two (*Asb2* and *Eif2s2*) isoform switches were identified at 440 and 550 days after γ -IR, respectively. Only two switches (*C3*, *Entpd5*) were detected in female LV's 440 days after simGCRsim-IR (**Supplementary Figure 1B**). Note, that *Stoml2* gene revealed isoform switches in 440 days males exposed to simGCRsim and 440 days females exposed to γ -IR (**Supplementary Figure 1B**, yellow highlighted). Interestingly, both males exposed to simGCRsim and females exposed to γ -IR showed significantly decreased usage (expression) of *Stoml2* functional isoform (**Supplementary Figure 1C**). *Stoml2* gene is a mitochondrial protein that is abundant in cardiomyocytes; its overexpression reduces cardiomyocyte apoptosis and myocardial injury, but its deficiency can mediate myocardial fibrosis and adverse cardiac remodeling by regulating the PI3K-Akt-mTOR signaling pathway⁹. The most prominent changes were observed for *Cetn2* and *Asb2* genes (**Supplementary Figures 2A, 2B**). It has been shown that *Cetn2* contributes to DNA repair mechanisms through stabilizing XPC complex, involved in global genome nucleotide excision repair¹⁰. Considering previous findings on expression changes of repair genes in astronauts' blood after the flight¹¹, this gene might also be involved in space IR-induced DNA repair. Loss of *Asb2* has been shown to impair cardiomyocyte differentiation.

In contrast to the previous report on the increased number of early post-IR-responsive alternatively spliced isoforms in human B-cells¹², we observed only a few isoform switches after a very long post-IR follow-up in mice (mouse lifetime studies). We noted that the expression of the *Stoml2* isoform was switched at 440 days post-IR in males and females exposed to simGCRsim. The *Stoml2* gene is a mitochondrial protein abundant in cardiomyocytes, its overexpression reduces cardiomyocyte apoptosis and myocardial injury, but deficiency can mediate myocardial fibrosis and adverse cardiac remodeling by regulating the PI3K-Akt-mTOR signaling pathway. At 440 days, males

exposed to simGCRsim and females exposed to gamma γ -IR showed significantly decreased usage (expression) of the *Stoml2* functional isoform, suggesting its important role in IR-induced processes.

References

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